

Supplementary Information

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Supplementary Fig. 1. Aqueous uranium concentrations in systems containing U^{VI} and 5 mM citrate with and without added *S. oneidensis* MR-1. Samples were filtered through 0.22 µm filters. Symbols and error bars depict 2 standard deviations of the mean of duplicate reactors. Where not visible, the error is smaller than the symbol size.

Supplementary Fig. 2. (a) Association of U^{VI} with oxidized MtrC after 1 h in systems containing 150 μM U^{VI} and 0.5 mM citrate at pH 7. Protein-associated U was separated from unbound U using 40 kDa size exclusion columns. Error bars depict the standard deviation of the mean of duplicate reactions, except for the protein-free control which was performed in triplicate. (b) Corresponding $\delta^{238}U$ values for unbound U^{VI} reported as a function of the remaining unbound U fraction. Filled and open symbols depict duplicate reactors and error bars show 2 standard deviations of the mean of triplicate measurements. (c) Association of U^{VI} with oxidized MtrC under the same conditions as for (a) but with 5 mM citrate. For the protein-free control, error bars depict the standard deviation of the mean of triplicate reactions. For the MtrC:U of 0.4, error bars depict the standard deviation of the mean of duplicate reactions and for the remaining systems only one measurement was performed. (d) Corresponding $\delta^{238}U$ values for unbound U^{VI} reported as a function of the remaining unbound U fraction. Filled and open symbols depict duplicate reactors and error bars show 2 standard deviations of the mean of triplicate measurements.

Supplementary Fig. 3. (left) Aqueous U speciation as a function of pH in systems containing 200 μM UO_2^{2+} , 5 mM EDTA^{4-} and 50 mM NaCl at 25 °C. (middle) Aqueous U speciation as a function of UO_2^{2+} concentration in systems containing 5 mM EDTA^{4-} and 50 mM NaCl at pH 7 and 25 °C. (right) Aqueous U speciation as a function of EDTA^{4-} concentration in systems containing 200 μM UO_2^{2+} and 50 mM NaCl at pH 7 and 25 °C. Calculations were performed using MINEQL+ v5 with updated formation constants^{1,2}.

Supplementary Fig. 4. Aqueous U speciation as a function of pH in systems containing 200 μM U and 5 mM sodium citrate at 25 °C. Calculations were performed using MINEQL+ v5 using updated formation constants for uranium carbonato and citrate complexes^{1,2}.

Supplementary Fig. 5. Aqueous U speciation as a function of U concentration, in systems containing 5 mM sodium citrate at 25 °C and pH 7, plotted as (a) % of total U and (b) species concentration. Calculations were performed using MINEQL+ v5 using updated formation constants for uranium carbonato and citrate complexes^{1,2}.

Supplementary Fig. 6. Linearized plots of isotope signatures, as a function of reaction progression, for reactors containing U^{VI} -EDTA incubated with either completely reduced MtrC (red. MtrC) or partially reduced MtrC (part. red. MtrC). Linear regressions represent Rayleigh distillation models and their corresponding isotope enrichment factors (ε) and R^2 values. These data and models correspond to those of Fig. 6c in the main manuscript.

Supplementary Fig. 7. (a) Concentration of U^{VI} , as a function of time, in reactors containing U^{VI} -EDTA incubated with *S. oneidensis*. Filled and open symbols depict duplicate reactors from two different batches of cells. **(b)** $\delta^{238}U$ values for U^{VI} reported as a function of the remaining U^{VI} fraction. Filled and open symbols depict duplicate reactors and error bars show 2 standard deviations of the mean of triplicate measurements. Rayleigh model curves for each duplicate reactor are shown in dashed lines, along with their corresponding isotope enrichment factors (ϵ).

Supplementary Fig. 8. (a) Concentration of U^{VI} , as a function of time, in reactors containing U^{VI} citrate incubated with *S. oneidensis* MR-1 and various concentrations of lactate. Values are plotted as the natural logarithm of the fraction of U^{VI} remaining and solid lines depict linear regressions for each reactor. These data correspond to a replicate experiment of that shown in Fig. 3a of the main manuscript. Different batches of *S. oneidensis* MR-1 cells result in slightly different isotope fractionation values (likely due to slight differences in growth conditions and gene expression/regulation) but the trends remain. **(b)** Linearized plots of isotope signatures, as a function of reaction progression, for reactors containing U^{VI} citrate incubated with *S. oneidensis* MR-1 at different concentrations of lactate. Each symbol shape represents the same treatments as for panel (a) and linear regressions represent Rayleigh distillation models and their corresponding isotope enrichment factors (ϵ). These data and models correspond to the batch replicates of those shown in Fig. 3b of the main manuscript.

Supplementary Fig. 9. Concentration of U^{VI} and U^{IV} in sterile control reactors containing $200 \mu\text{M}$ U^{VI} and 5 mM sodium citrate. Symbols and error bars depict 1 standard deviation of the mean of triplicate reactors. Where not visible, the error is smaller than the symbol size.

Supplementary Fig. 10. (a) Total U, aqueous U and aqueous U^{VI} & U^{IV} concentrations after 5 days in abiotic control systems containing U^{VI} , 5 mM EDTA and 20 mM lactate. Aqueous U concentrations were determined after filtration through $0.22 \mu\text{m}$ filters. (b) Total U, aqueous U and aqueous U^{VI} & U^{IV} concentrations after 5 days in systems containing U^{VI} , 5 mM EDTA, 20 mM lactate and *S. oneidensis*. Aqueous U concentrations were determined after filtration through $0.22 \mu\text{m}$ filters. Columns and error bars depict the standard deviation of the mean of four reactors.

Supplementary Table 1. U^{VI} reduction rate constants and corresponding R^2 values for linear regressions of the natural logarithm of the fraction of U^{VI} remaining as a function of time.

System	Treatment	Rate constant (h^{-1})	R^2
MR-1 + U(VI)-citrate (Fig. 2a)	11×10^8 cells mL^{-1}	-0.364	0.998
	2.3×10^8 cells mL^{-1}	-0.082	0.993
	0.7×10^8 cells mL^{-1}	-0.034	0.996
	0.23×10^8 cells mL^{-1}	-0.013	0.998
MR-1 + U(VI)-citrate A replicate (Fig. 3a)	0.5 mM lactate	-0.160	0.983
	0.3 mM lactate	-0.128	0.994
	0.1 mM lactate	-0.082	0.992
	0.05 mM lactate	-0.044	0.996
MR-1 + U(VI)-citrate B replicate (Supplementary Fig. 8a)	0.5 mM lactate	-0.158	0.994
	0.3 mM lactate	-0.150	0.992
	0.1 mM lactate	-0.088	0.993
CFE + U(VI)-citrate (Fig. 4b)	0.05 mM lactate	-0.078	0.988
		-0.002	0.987
MR-1 + U(VI)-EDTA (Supplementary Fig. 7a)	Replicate A	-1.286	0.991
	Replicate B	-1.108	0.989

Supplementary Table 2. Fractionation factors ($\epsilon^{Rayleigh}$) and corresponding R^2 values for linearized Rayleigh distillation models of isotope signatures as a function of the natural logarithm of the fraction of U^{VI} remaining in experimental reactors.

System	Treatment	$\epsilon^{Rayleigh}$ (‰)	R^2
MR-1 + U(VI)-citrate (Fig. 2b)	11×10^8 cells mL ⁻¹	0.47	0.94
	2.3×10^8 cells mL ⁻¹	0.48	0.98
	0.7×10^8 cells mL ⁻¹	0.50	0.97
	0.23×10^8 cells mL ⁻¹	0.48	0.97
MR-1 + U(VI)-citrate A replicate (Fig. 3b)	0.5 mM lactate	0.58	0.99
	0.3 mM lactate	0.60	0.99
	0.1 mM lactate	0.66	0.97
	0.05 mM lactate	0.81	1.00
MR-1 + U(VI)-citrate B replicate (Supplementary Fig. 8b)	0.5 mM lactate	0.49	0.98
	0.3 mM lactate	0.53	1.00
	0.1 mM lactate	0.62	0.98
CFE + U(VI)-citrate (Fig. 4c)	0.05 mM lactate	0.63	0.99
	Replicate A	0.95	0.98
Fully reduced MtrC + U(VI)-EDTA (Fig. 6c & Supplementary Fig. 6)	Replicate B	1.05	0.99
	Replicate A	0.16	0.74
Partially reduced MtrC + U(VI)-EDTA (Fig. 6c & Supplementary Fig. 6)	Replicate B	0.16	0.78
	Replicate A	0.86	0.99
MR-1 + U(VI)-EDTA (Supplementary Fig. 7b)	Replicate B	0.80	1.00
	Replicate A	1.08	0.99
	Replicate B	0.99	0.98

Supplementary References

1. Guillaumont, R. *et al.* *Update on the chemical thermodynamics of uranium, neptunium, plutonium, americium and technetium.* (OECD Nuclear Energy Agency, 2003).
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